

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, Alison K. Post, and R. Chelsea Nagy

HYR-SENSE Field Trip
(Credit: Casey Jenson)

Quick Updates

- 14 Earth Lab team members attended the annual Ecological Society of America meeting in August to present their work
- Research from Earth Lab's Fire Team was featured in [the Washington Post](#)
- Earth Lab's Education team published their [Case Study of the Earth Data Science Corps](#) in the Journal of Statistics and Data Science Education.
- Earth Lab & ESIIIL team members co-hosted numerous events including: a summit, NASA HYRSENSE training, data short course, and several working groups. Read more about ESIIIL events [here](#).
- Earth Data Analytics certificate students gave their final presentations, watch them [here](#).
- **Join our Team!** Earth Lab is now accepting applications for a Fire Risk & Forest Resilience Project Manager. Visit [our website](#) to learn more and apply by September 27th, 2024.

Summer Graduate Research

This summer, Earth Lab hosted several Graduate Research Assistants (GRA) who worked with an Earth Lab mentor to develop an independent project. Each GRA gave a 5-minute Ignite-style talk to describe their final project.

Data Science Training in the Data Era - Asia Kaiser

Managing Ecological Transformation via Carbon Storage - Anirudh Maiya

Towards Mapping Fuel Mass & Flammability of the Built Environment in the US - Max Cook

Dynamic - Risk Index for Wildfire - Daksha Singhal

New Team Member Q&A

Kyle Manley joined the Earth Lab team as a postdoctoral associate. Get to know Kyle in our Q&A below:

1. What is your background?

- I hold a BA from CU's own ENVS department and recently completed my PhD in Earth System Science at UC Irvine. Most recently, I worked on developing new approaches using social sensing and machine learning to map, model, and value cultural ecosystem services and assess future impacts to these non-material benefits under climate change.

2. What are you most looking forward to in your new position?

- I'm excited to apply my ecosystem service background to the field of wildfire/Rx, which is a new area for me. I'm especially excited to learn from the wealth of wildfire experience among the talented people at Earth Lab and ESII!

3. What is your favorite national park

- As a Colorado native it feels traitorous to not say any of the amazing parks here in CO, but during my time in CA I really fell in love with Joshua Tree!

Kyle Manley
Postdoctoral Associate

Macrosystems Ecology for All

Several Earth Lab team members assisted with the 2024 Macrosystems Ecology for All (MEFA) annual meeting held at CU Boulder, hosted by the [Macrosystems Ecology for All Research Coordination Network](#). The goal of the meeting is to bring together faculty in teaching-focused positions and early career scientists to learn macrosystems ecology data skills and develop collaborative projects. There were about 40 in-person and 15 virtual attendees. From Earth Lab, Casey Jenson (Program Assistant) facilitated the remote attendees and Alison Post (Program Manager), Nate Quarderer (Education Director), and Elsa Culler (Curriculum Developer) led environmental data science trainings using the [PhenoCam Network](#) and Codespaces (via GitHub). Day one included an overview of the PhenoCam Network and the type of data available, and Day 2 covered how to access and visualize PhenoCam data, including how to make a gif (short movie) showing the changing seasons at a PhenoCam site. Check out the lesson [here](#).

Team Social Events

Earth Lab hosted multiple social events to connect with each other, summer students, the NC CASC, and ESIL team members. These included happy hours, a Geology hike, a welcome breakfast, an ice cream social picnic, and a pizza party!

Earth Lab, ESIL, and NC CASC team members at our ice cream social and welcome picnic.

Team members at the Geology hike in The Boulder Foothills led by our resident expert geologist, Matt Rossi.

ESIL Working Groups

This summer, ESIL hosted 3 working group meetings in Boulder, CO. ESIL is currently accepting applications for working groups for the 2025 cohort! Visit [their website](#) to learn more & apply!

[Apply Now](#)

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